

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

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Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

T1.3_UK Lab 2nd Co-creation Workshop Report

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Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
18/04/2024	1.0	First draft
19/04/2024	1.1	Revision & speakers contributions and interventions

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Hardwick Hall Hotel Sedgefield TS21 2EH

EVENT DATE: 17/04/2024, 10:30 AM – 17/04/2024, 5:30 PM.

EVENT TITLE: Energi Coast Regional Supply Chain Showcase Event

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical attendance

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Exhibition and Conference

EVENT AFFILIATION: *North East England's Offshore Wind Cluster*

LEAD ORGANISER: Energi Coast NOF, Eastgate Engineering (Main Sponsor)

CO-ORGANISERS: University of York, MARINEWIND stand

LANGUAGE: English

CONCEPT: University of York interacted and collaborated with the Energi Coast Regional Supply Chain Showcase

OBJECTIVES:

The Energi Coast NOF's event primary objectives were to facilitate supply chain industry engagement aimed at exploring innovative production and market strategies to accelerate the deployment of floating offshore wind in the North East of England waters. Specifically, the event focused on exploring the collective industry insights and identifying key barriers and enablers that can drive progress in crucial areas of offshore wind technology.

The event attendees had the opportunity to:

- Gain deep insights into market strategies tailored for the deployment of floating offshore wind, understanding the unique challenges and opportunities associated with this emerging sector.
- Collaborate closely with industry experts and peers, fostering an environment conducive to knowledge sharing, networking, and collaboration.
- Contribute actively to meaningful discussions aimed at driving progress in the offshore wind sector, leveraging collective expertise and insights to identify actionable solutions and opportunities for innovation.

MARINEWIND aims at increasing societal acceptance of FOWT facilities and installations through science-based evidence and tools addressing misperception phenomena from citizens. The ultimate ambition of MARINEWIND is to support the investment of both private sector and public authorities in FOWT while accelerating their commercialisation and identifying critical environmental and societal support and solutions to techno-economic barriers to their wide deployment in various European geographical areas.⁶

The main objectives of the project are:

- To increase awareness and to provide a basis for policy-makers and stakeholders for developing political and business agendas open to FOWT opportunities.
- To increase societal acceptance of FOWT through science-based evidence and tools, facilitating the interaction with fishermen, tourists and other relevant stakeholders.

- To promote the development of financial analysis and solutions that can support further investment in FOWT.
- To provide a wide potential for replication and long-term viability of FOWT.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The event aimed to engage representatives from diverse sectors involved in the offshore wind energy sector, including public authorities (Crown Estate), supply chains (Smulders, SMD, and MJR), engineering firms (Eastgate engineering and Deyer), research institutes (University of York), and various industry stakeholders including small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Here's a breakdown of the specific actors involved from each category:

- Industry: This category encompassed technology and project developers, representing the forefront of innovation and project implementation within the offshore wind sector.
- Supply chain: Participants included stakeholders involved in various aspects of the supply chain, such as port infrastructure developers, cable design and installation experts, original equipment manufacturers (OEM) companies, technology and project developers, as well as trade associations representing industries such as fisheries and tourism, crucial for understanding and mitigating potential impacts.
- Research institutes: Scientific and research community members contributed their expertise to the event, providing insights and advancements in offshore wind technology and sustainability practices.
- Public authorities: Policymakers at various levels of government were engaged to ensure alignment of regulatory frameworks with industry needs and sustainability objectives.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: *number of participants and graph with percentage of participation from each of the 5-Helix stakeholder categories.*

The number of participants in this event was 125. The graph and table below provide more details on the percentage of participants based on the stakeholder category.

Sector	Company name	Delegate Name
Ports	Able UK	Neil Etherington
	Clarksons Port Services	Stephen Smith
	PD Ports	Andrew Crowe
	Port of Blyth	Alasdair Kerr
	Port of Middlesbrough (AV Dawson Group)	Richard Booth FICS
	Port of Tyne	Craig Morton
	Port Training Services	Paul Parry
	SeAH Wind	David Jack
	SeAH Wind	Peter Ivey and Nicholas Perry
	Clarksons Port Services	Paul Hutchinson and Steve Smith
	Energi Coast	Hannah Smiles
	AV Dawson Group	Richard Booth
	Cyan Renewables	Stuart Thornton
	PD Ports	Emily Bulmer
	Port of Blyth	James Brown
	Port of Sunderland	Sven Richards
Port of Tyne	Dan Burke	
Public Authorities	North of Tyne Combined Authority	Elizabeth Lunn
	Tees Valley Combined Authority	Chris Rowell
	The Crown Estate	David Hodkinson
	Advance Northumberland	Rachel Ryder Michael Harriott
	Teesside International Airport	Peter Walker William Cummock
	Tees Valley Supply Chain	Lesley Hawke Steve Turnbull

Sector	Company name	Delegate Name
Supply Chain	Correll Group	Geoff Briggs
	Eastgate Engineering	David Brennan
	MJR Power & Automation	Ryan Reilly
	SMD	Richard Bray
	Smulders	Geert Boutsen
	Equinor	Tom Nightingale
	GE Vernova (Dogger Bank Offshore Wind)	Bill Mcloughlin
	Smulders	Stuart McMullan
	Dyer Engineering	Daniel Tracey Richard Bradley
	Eastgate Engineering	Paul Mclaughlin Anthony Fiske
	NRL	Emma Lowden Allan Stevenson
	RelyOn Nutec	Helen Dunn Graham Wood Yasmine Milne
	Tricore Technical Services	Paul Bass Emma Bass
	AkzoNobel	Rob Conte
	Allerton Steel	Andrew Gatenby
	Applebridge Family	Matt Exley
	Barrier Fabrication	Robert Smaje
	Brand Energy & Infrastructure Services UK	Christian Douma
	Carboline	James Lawson Rob Allan
	Ellis Patents	Noman Shabir
	Francis Brown	Jamie Brown
	Helippe	Paul Johnson
	KAEFER UK & Ireland	Trevor Woodward Ciaran Clifford
	Maclea International	Chloe Ross
	MacArtney Underwater Technology Group	Thomas Ivanic
	Mayteck	Alan Gray
	Metec Group	Graeme Crow
	Pentagon Freight Services	Matthew Bray
	RHI Industrials	John Burdon
	Roxtec	Dayna Ferguson
	RS Group	Amy Quinn
	Samuel Knight International	Dan Kerr
	Severfield Group PLC	David Oswin
	Smulders	Stuart McMullan
	T.H.E Section Bending Co	Robert Bunting
	Union Fasteners	David Barber
	Universal Matter	Andrew Curry
	Veolia	Maxine Thompson
	WIKA Instruments	Tracey Crawford
	Wolviston Group	Steve Guest Mike Wood

Sector	Company name	Delegate Name
Technology/Project Developers	CleanWatts	Ian Finch
	Osbit	Thomas Ashley
	GE Renewable Energy	Jonny Corrigan
	A Squared Engineering	Andrew Robson Marie Difolco Kalpesh Barshi
	Acuity Robotics	Jason Liu
	BES Group Asset Reliability (Strainstall)	Paul Dekker Kleyn
	Jan De Nul	Richard Cordes
	Kinewell Energy	Henna Bains
	MAN Energy Solutions	Andrew Tait
	MPI Offshore / Van Oord	Craig Hillen
	Rope Access in London	Kevin Mezzone
	SMD	Joanne Henderson
	Tekmar	Marc Bell
	VRAI International	Mark O'Reilly
Walker Subsea Engineering	Nathan Watson	
Academia/Research Organisation	University of York	Paola Zerilli and Ahmed Djeddi
	ORE Catapult	Tony Quinn
	Middlesbrough College	James Barwick and Francis Nyavanhu
	Durham University	Simon Hogg
	Newcastle University	Abby Reeds
	Teesside University	Nashwan Dawood
Consultancy Services	Horizon Stays	Michaela Tipp Denis Shail
	Horizon Works Marketing	Samantha Vassallo Richard Holmes
	Scarab4	Jane Gatiss Mark Gatiss
	4MS	Martin Wykman
	Applus UK	Sam McInnes
	CFB Risk Management	Rachel Chambers
	Correll Group	Peter Dinsdale
	Entrepreneurs' Forum	Michael Dixon
	Harrison Network	Mark Hurley
	Heightec	Simon Beck
	Innovation Supernetwork	Lynda Sale
	K2 Construction Management	James Grant and David Gardner
	M A R	Ray Bland
	Proeon Systems Limited	Peter Lascelles
Rise Learning Group	Jen Tait	
Spirit Advisory	Chris Jones	
Funding/Investors	NOF	Caroline Lofthouse
	Wilton Group	Bill Scott OBE DL

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 TONY QUINN, ENERGI COAST CHAIR (DIRECTOR AT ORE CATAPULT)

During the presentation, the speaker explored the UK's leadership in the Offshore Wind energy sector. Outlining the critical role played by advanced infrastructure and cutting-edge technology, stressing how these factors position the UK as a frontrunner on the global stage. For instance, the speaker highlighted ongoing infrastructural developments aimed at fortifying the UK's maritime capabilities, including the expansion of port facilities and the enhancement of grid connections, crucial for the efficient deployment and operation of offshore wind energy projects. Moreover, the speaker highlighted the importance of utilising a highly skilled workforce specialised in Floating offshore wind technology. Furthermore, the speaker discussed various training programs and educational initiatives geared towards cultivating expertise within the UK's offshore wind sector, emphasising the collaborative efforts between industry and academia in this venture.

In emphasising the significance of investing in floating offshore wind energy for sustainable industrial growth, the speaker discussed the economic and environmental benefits inherent in such endeavours. They focused on the spillover effects of investing in the floating offshore wind energy sector, including job creation, reduced carbon emissions, and heightened energy security, all contributing to the goal of meeting the UK renewable energy objective of deploying 50 GW by 2030 through renewable energy sources. Furthermore, the speaker shed light on the UK's vibrant renewable energy cluster, illustrating how the current dynamic ecosystem serves as a breeding ground for innovation and collaboration. They provided concrete examples of successful industry-academia partnerships and highlighted the pivotal role played by research institutes and industry associations in propelling advancements in floating offshore wind technology.

In discussing initiatives like the offshore manufacturing scheme, the speaker commented on the strategic measures undertaken to attract private and foreign investments into the floating offshore wind sector. Focusing on how such initiatives not only bolster investor confidence but also fuel competitiveness on the global stage by facilitating access to crucial funding and resources. Moreover, the speaker underscored the importance of fostering collaboration between various stakeholders, including academic institutions, private enterprises, manufacturers, and SMEs, to optimise offshore wind farm capabilities. They expounded on how synergistic collaborations drive innovation, streamline processes, and ultimately enhance the UK's competitive advantage in the offshore wind market.

Lastly, the speaker emphasised the need for a multifaceted approach to sustain sectoral growth and improve the UK's standing in the floating offshore wind energy market. Stressing the need of increasing manufacturing capacity and attracting investments to bolster the sector's resilience and fortify the UK's leadership position. Overall, the speaker's comprehensive insights provided a nuanced understanding of the factors contributing to the UK's ascendancy in the floating offshore wind energy sector, underlining the country's unwavering commitment to pioneering sustainable energy solutions on a global scale.

2.2 DAVID HODKINSON, THE CROWN ESTATE

The speaker started by discussing the Crown Estate's purpose, which is to foster lasting and shared prosperity for the nation, emphasising the distinct attributes that underpin The Crown Estate's approach, including its long-term perspective, independence, simplicity of role, and the power to convene and catalyse actions. The speaker highlighted The Crown Estate's focus on addressing critical national needs, such as energy security and the Net Zero agenda, economic growth and productivity, the growing pressure on urban centres, and biodiversity loss. The speaker emphasised the importance of aligning The Crown Estate's activities with these overarching national objectives to drive meaningful impact and create value for the country. Also, the speaker outlined the strategic objectives, which include being a leader in supporting the UK towards a net-zero carbon and energy-secure future, stewarding the UK's natural environment and biodiversity, and responsibly generating value and financial returns for the country by creating inclusive communities and supporting equality, economic growth, and productivity. Furthermore, the speaker underscored the importance of generating value beyond financial returns, emphasising The Crown Estate's commitment to fostering social and environmental sustainability through its activities and initiatives.

In relation to the Celtic Sea Blueprint: the speaker provided an in-depth overview of the Celtic Sea Blueprint, which serves as the evidence base for a call to action to accelerate offshore wind development in the Celtic Sea. Detailing the minimum infrastructure requirements for delivering 4.5 GW of floating offshore wind capacity in the region, highlighting the significant economic benefits associated with the program. The speaker outlined the specific infrastructure components needed for the program's success, including integration ports, assembly ports, marshalling ports, and offshore wind turbines. Additionally, the speaker discussed the capacity risks and barriers identified in the Blueprint, providing valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities for offshore wind development in the Celtic Sea.

Lastly, the speaker introduced The Crown Estate's Supply Chain Accelerator, a £50 million investment initiative aimed at supporting the growth of the UK's offshore wind supply chain. They provided a detailed overview of the Accelerator's objectives, including its focus on early-stage project development, match funding opportunities, and alignment with sustainability principles. The speaker emphasised The Crown Estate's collaborative approach to co-investing with UK-based promoters to drive innovation and create value for the offshore wind industry. They highlighted the specific areas targeted by the Accelerator, such as floating platform components, dynamic cables, wet storage infrastructure, and skills transition facilities. Additionally, the speaker discussed the broader impact of the Accelerator on the UK's offshore wind sector, including job creation, economic growth, and technological innovation.

2.3 DAVID JACK, SEAH WIND

The speaker from SeAH winds provided valuable insights into the business sector, industry region, and value chain dynamics of SeAH Wind Ltd., a prominent player in the offshore wind sector. They highlighted SeAH Wind's focus on renewable energy, particularly offshore wind, within the global, European, and United Kingdom contexts. The speaker underscored SeAH Wind's key product offerings,

including large-size monopile foundations, and outlined their investment timescale, production capacity, and location in Teeswork, England.

SeAH Winds - Projects: The speaker delved into SeAH Wind's involvement in significant offshore wind projects, such as Hornsea 3 and Norfolk Vanguard East and West. They provided details on project locations, turbine sizes, construction timelines, and key contracts, emphasising SeAH Wind's role in supplying foundations for these landmark projects. Additionally, the speaker highlighted the scale and importance of these projects, such as Hornsea 3 being the world's largest single approved offshore wind farm and Norfolk Vanguard East and West contributing to the UK's offshore wind hub.

Supply Chain Opportunities: The speaker outlined various supply chain opportunities available through SeAH Wind's projects, spanning factory construction, monopile projects, and operational phases. They detailed specific requirements for suppliers, such as metal staircases, welding consumables, logistics services, NDT contractors, and fabrication jigs/platforms. Additionally, the speaker highlighted future potential opportunities and encouraged interested parties to participate in tender processes.

Overall, the speaker's contributions shed light on SeAH Wind's strategic positioning, project involvements, and supply chain dynamics, providing valuable insights for stakeholders seeking to engage with the company and capitalise on emerging opportunities in the offshore wind sector.

2.4 GEERT BOUTSEN, SMULDERS

The speaker provided valuable insights into Smulders' role as a leading manufacturer of steel structures for the offshore wind industry, highlighting their extensive experience since the inception of offshore wind in 2001. They emphasised Smulders' track record of providing foundations and substations to over 70 offshore wind projects, totaling nearly 34GW of output. The speaker outlined Smulders' current projects, including the fabrication and delivery of transition pieces for various offshore wind farms, underscoring the company's strategic focus on delivering high-quality steel structures to support the industry's growth.

Offshore Wind Foundations and Substations: the speaker detailed Smulders' involvement in several key offshore wind projects, including supplying transition pieces, jackets, and gravity-based foundations. They highlighted specific projects, such as the SeaMade Offshore Wind Farm in Belgium and the Dogger Bank Offshore Wind Farm in the UK, where Smulders is providing transition pieces to support turbine installations. Additionally, the speaker mentioned Smulders' capabilities in manufacturing floating foundations, jackets, and other offshore wind structures, showcasing the company's versatility in meeting project requirements.

Our Organization and Supply Chain Requirements: the speaker provided an overview of Smulders' organisational structure, highlighting its global presence with offices and facilities across Europe and India. They outlined the requirements for local suppliers and subcontractors, emphasising the need for compliance with strict contractual requirements, certifications, and codes of conduct. The speaker also discussed the offshore supply chain requirements, including the capacity to deliver at expected production rates, adherence to just-in-time delivery schemes, and financial stability to support project commitments.

Products and Services for Potential Applicants: the speaker outlined the products and services for which companies may apply to participate in Smulders' supply chain. These include subcontracting of steel structures, fabrication, assembly, and coating/galvanising of platform structures, as well as various services such as NDT, QA inspections, welding/fabrication, and MRO. Additionally, the speaker mentioned equipment procurement and installation services for electrical systems into foundations, highlighting opportunities for potential suppliers to contribute to offshore wind projects.

Overall, the speaker's contributions shed light on Smulders' purpose, strategy, and drivers in the offshore wind industry, providing valuable insights for stakeholders interested in engaging with the company and participating in the offshore wind supply chain.

2.5 DAVID BRENNAN, EASTGATE ENGINEERING

The speaker highlighted the immense potential of the UK floating offshore wind industry, which is still in its early stages but rapidly expanding. With 14.7GW of operational capacity and a pipeline of planned projects totaling 23GW, the industry is poised for significant growth. The ambitious targets of 50GW by 2030 and 125GW by 2050 underscore the crucial role of offshore wind in achieving the nation's Net Zero goal.

The speaker also discussed the government initiatives such as freeports, capital allowance support, and investment zones that are providing a favourable environment for offshore wind investment. Tax reliefs, innovation funding, and investment schemes are incentivizing industry growth and fostering innovation, particularly in areas like floating offshore wind technology. Collaboration with organisations like the Offshore Renewable Energy Catapult (OREC) and the Offshore Wind Manufacturing Investment Scheme further support research, innovation, and infrastructure development.

Northeast Readiness for Growth: The Northeast region of England is well-positioned to capitalise on the growth opportunities in offshore wind. Critical port infrastructure, a skilled workforce, and a growing supply chain contribute to the region's readiness for expansion. Collaboration between local universities, colleges, and industry players ensures the availability of specialised skills and expertise. The region boasts a mature and experienced supply chain capable of managing the full project cycle, from installation to fit out.

Transferable Skills and Experienced Supply Chain: Transferable skills from the oil and gas industry, coupled with high-quality training and education standards, provide a strong foundation for workforce development in offshore wind. Local manufacturing and production capabilities for key components like transition pieces, offshore substations, and monopiles are essential for meeting long-term industry goals. The Northeast's mature supply chain offers cost-efficient solutions for project execution, providing certainty and reliability for developers and contractors alike.

In conclusion, the speaker highlighted the collaborative efforts between government, industry, and academia to support the growth of the UK offshore wind sector. With a focus on innovation, skills development, and infrastructure investment, the Northeast region is poised to play a leading role in the industry's expansion and contribute significantly to the nation's renewable energy targets.

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

3.1 DISCUSSION PANEL - WHY NORTH EAST ENGLAND: ELIZABETH LUNN - NORTH OF TYNE COMBINED AUTHORITY, CHRIS ROWELL - TEES VALLEY COMBINED AUTHORITY, DAVID JACK - SEAH WIND, SIMON HOGG - (ENERGI COAST INNOVATION GROUP LEAD), AND GEERT BOUTSEN - SMULDERS

The panel discussion focused on the vision of positioning North East England as a premier destination for offshore wind sector investment and development. With a clear purpose in mind, the speakers outlined strategic objectives aimed at fostering collaboration, driving engagement, and promoting investments in the region's offshore wind industry.

Networking and investments emerged as central themes during the discussion. Speakers emphasised the importance of leveraging networking opportunities to attract investment and capitalise on the region's assets. North East England's excellent location for offshore wind farm projects, coupled with available infrastructure and ports, creates a compelling proposition for investors seeking growth opportunities in renewable energy.

Strategic partnerships between education and industry stakeholders were highlighted as essential for addressing the skills gap and driving innovation in the offshore wind sector. By facilitating pioneering collaborations, North East England aims to create a conducive environment for knowledge exchange and skills development, ultimately positioning itself as a hub of excellence in offshore wind technology and engineering.

Engagement with offshore wind operators and supply chain stakeholders is crucial for understanding current and future skills demand. Through active engagement, the region seeks to better align skills provision with industry needs, ensuring a steady pipeline of talent to support the sector's growth trajectory. This collaborative approach not only enhances workforce diversity and inclusivity but also fosters a culture of innovation and excellence.

Promotion of careers in the offshore wind sector is another key aspect of North East England's strategy. By showcasing the region's rich culture, heritage, and advanced manufacturing capabilities, stakeholders aim to attract skilled professionals and investors alike. Moreover, the transition of SMEs and companies from traditional industries to offshore wind projects underscores the region's commitment to sustainable economic development and job creation.

Despite the opportunities presented by the offshore wind industry, speakers also addressed challenges such as high supply chain costs. However, they underscored the importance of reducing costs through collaboration and innovation while ensuring profitability for suppliers. By overcoming barriers and capitalising on networking opportunities, North East England aims to solidify its position as a global leader in offshore wind skills provision and drive sustainable growth in the sector for years to come.

3.2 DISCUSSION PANEL: NORTH EAST ENGLAND'S PORTS & VESSELS - STRENGTHS AND CAPABILITIES TO TAKE OUR REGION INTO DEEP WATER PROJECTS.

The panel discussion on North East England's Ports & Vessels for deep water projects delved into critical issues facing the offshore wind industry. Hosted by Ian Finch from CleanWatts, the panel featured Alasdair Kerr from the Port of Blyth, Craig Morton representing the Port of Tyne, Neil Etherington from Able UK, Andrew Crowe of PD Ports, and Richard Booth FICS from the Port of Middlesbrough/Cockfield Knight.

One of the central themes of the discussion was the lack of government understanding of the offshore wind industry's needs and requirements. Panellists expressed concern that this lack of understanding is impeding progress toward the UK's ambitious renewable energy targets. To reach the objective of deploying 50 GW of renewable energy by 2030, the panel emphasised the urgent need for government support and proactive measures.

A critical point highlighted during the discussion was the necessity to construct five new ports every year for the next six years to meet the 50 GW target. However, the construction timeline for each port, from inception to completion, typically spans five to six years. This underscores the urgency for immediate action and substantial investment in port infrastructure to support the offshore wind sector's rapid expansion.

Despite the industry's readiness and the region's potential, the lack of government understanding poses a significant barrier to progress. The panel stressed the importance of bridging this gap through enhanced communication, collaboration, and proactive policymaking. Without government support and alignment with industry needs, achieving the 50 GW target and advancing the offshore wind sector's growth trajectory will be challenging.

In conclusion, the panel discussion underscored the critical role of government understanding and support in driving the offshore wind industry forward. It emphasised the need for timely and strategic investments in port infrastructure to facilitate the sector's expansion and meet ambitious renewable energy targets. Collaborative efforts between industry stakeholders and policymakers are essential to overcome barriers and unlock the full potential of North East England's ports and vessels for deep water projects.

Other points that were discussed are:

- Lack of space for new ports: The panel recognized the scarcity of available space for the construction of new ports, particularly in densely populated coastal areas. Addressing this challenge requires strategic planning and innovative approaches to maximise existing port infrastructure's capacity, as well as exploring alternative locations for port development and expansion.
- Lack of investments in ports and infrastructure: Panellists highlighted the need for substantial investments in port infrastructure to meet the growing demands of the offshore wind industry. They emphasised the importance of public and private sector collaboration to secure funding

for port development projects and accelerate infrastructure upgrades. Investing in ports and infrastructure is critical for enhancing the industry's capacity, efficiency, and competitiveness in the global market.

- Lack of necessary ports for floating offshore wind farms: Panellists underscored the critical need for ports capable of supporting floating offshore wind farms, which play a crucial role in achieving renewable energy targets. They emphasised the urgency of identifying suitable locations for new ports and investing in infrastructure to accommodate the unique requirements of floating wind projects.

4 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The 1st of the three co-creation workshops for T1.3 with regards to the UK Lab has been mainly dedicated to barriers perceived by the stakeholders for the investment on FOWTs, and to potential enablers. Thanks to the data collected, the next two workshops will then focus on solutions and policies to ease the installation of Offshore Wind Plants. The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the workshop on one side, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the other.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Lack of investments in ports and infrastructure: Inadequate investments in port infrastructure can impede the deployment and operation of floating offshore wind projects, limiting industry growth potential. Solution: Governments can allocate funding for port development projects through infrastructure investment programs or renewable energy initiatives. Leveraging private sector capital through public-private partnerships or project financing schemes can also help bridge funding gaps and accelerate the construction of essential infrastructure for the floating offshore wind sector.</p>	<p>The UK boasts advanced infrastructure and technology that can support the development and operation of floating offshore wind farms. This includes specialised vessels, ports, and manufacturing facilities tailored to the needs of the offshore wind industry. Advanced technology such as advanced materials, sensors, and automation can enhance the efficiency and reliability of offshore wind energy production</p>
<p>High energy costs: High energy costs can make renewable energy projects, such as floating offshore wind, less economically competitive compared to traditional energy sources. Solution: Investment in research and development to improve the efficiency of floating offshore wind technology can help reduce operational costs and make it more economically viable. Additionally, government incentives or subsidies can further offset high energy costs and encourage investment in renewable energy projects.</p>	<p>The UK has a skilled workforce with expertise in various aspects of the offshore wind sector, including engineering, project management, and maintenance. These skilled personnel play a crucial role in the design, construction, and operation of floating offshore wind farms, contributing to the sector's success and competitiveness on a global scale.</p>
<p>High supply chain costs and prices: High supply chain costs and prices can hinder the scalability and profitability of floating offshore</p>	<p>Investing in floating offshore wind is not only crucial for meeting renewable energy targets but also for driving sustainable</p>

<p>wind projects, potentially deterring investors. Solution: Implementing strategies to optimise supply chain management, such as bulk purchasing, standardisation of components, and fostering collaboration among suppliers, can help reduce costs. Moreover, incentivizing the use of recycled materials or local sourcing can contribute to cost savings and sustainability.</p>	<p>industrial growth. FOWT projects create jobs, stimulate economic development, and contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions. By prioritising investment in OWT, the UK establishes itself as a leader in sustainable energy production and drives innovation in the broader renewable energy sector.</p>
<p>Lack of space for new ports: Limited space for new ports can restrict the development of infrastructure necessary for the expansion of the floating offshore wind sector. Solution: Repurposing underutilised land or existing port facilities, as well as exploring alternative port configurations such as floating or modular ports, can help address space limitations. Collaboration between government agencies, local authorities, and private investors is crucial to identify suitable locations and secure funding for port development projects.</p>	<p>The UK is home to one of the most advanced renewable energy clusters globally, comprising companies, research institutions, and government agencies focused on developing and deploying renewable energy technologies. This cluster fosters collaboration, knowledge exchange, and innovation, providing a supportive ecosystem for the growth of the floating offshore wind industry.</p>
<p>Lack of necessary ports in the northeast of England: Insufficient port infrastructure in key regions like the northeast of England can impede the achievement of renewable energy targets and hinder industry growth. Solution: Government intervention and strategic planning are essential to prioritise and fast-track the development of port facilities in areas with high potential for floating offshore wind projects. Public-private partnerships and investment incentives can incentivize private sector involvement in port construction and expansion initiatives.</p>	<p>The offshore manufacturing scheme offers financial incentives and support to companies engaged in the manufacturing of offshore wind components, including floating offshore wind technology. This scheme aims to stimulate investment, create jobs, and enhance the competitiveness of the UK's offshore wind industry by reducing production costs and attracting private and foreign investors</p>
<p>Lack of government understanding of needs: Without an understanding of the requirements and challenges faced by the floating offshore wind sector, governments may fail to implement effective policies and support mechanisms. Solution: Engaging with industry stakeholders through consultations, advisory boards, and research collaborations can enhance government understanding of sector needs. Furthermore, education and training programs for policymakers and regulators can improve awareness of the technical, economic, and environmental aspects of floating offshore wind energy.</p>	<p>The UK's pioneering capabilities in offshore wind technology, coupled with its extensive experience in the renewable energy sector, position it as a global leader in floating offshore wind. This leadership is driven by innovation, research, and development initiatives that push the boundaries of what is possible in offshore wind energy production, setting the standard for other nations to follow</p>
	<p>The UK industrial growth plan outlines strategies and initiatives to promote growth, innovation, and competitiveness across various sectors, including renewable</p>

	<p>energy. This plan includes targeted investments, policy support, and collaboration efforts aimed at advancing the development and deployment of floating offshore wind technology, driving industrial growth, and creating economic opportunities.</p>
	<p>Collaboration between academic institutions, private sector companies, manufacturers, and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) facilitates knowledge sharing, technology transfer, and innovation in the offshore wind sector. This collaboration enhances the UK's offshore wind farm capabilities, improves project efficiency, and strengthens the country's position in the global offshore wind market.</p>
	<p>The UK's favourable conditions, including its geographical location, natural resources, supportive policy environment, and established industry infrastructure, position it to capitalise on the enablers mentioned above and emerge as a key player in the floating offshore wind market. By leveraging these advantages effectively, the UK can drive growth, innovation, and leadership in the FOWT sector.</p>
	<p>Expanding manufacturing capacity and attracting investments are critical for sustaining the growth momentum of the floating offshore wind sector in the UK. This requires continuous investment in infrastructure, technology, and workforce development to meet increasing demand and maintain investor confidence in the long-term viability and competitiveness of the UK's FOWT industry.</p>
	<p>Incremental investments and timely project delivery are essential for enhancing the UK's position in the floating offshore wind sector. By committing to strategic investments and streamlining project development processes, the UK can accelerate the deployment of FOWT projects, capitalise on market opportunities, and strengthen its leadership in the global offshore wind industry.</p>

